

THE USE OF DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL GAMES IN MATHEMATICS LEARNING: A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

EL USO DE JUEGOS DIGITALES EDUCATIVOS EN EL APRENDIZAJE DE LAS MATEMÁTICAS: UNA REVISIÓN SISTEMÁTICA DE LA LITERATURA

O USO DE JOGOS EDUCACIONAIS DIGITAIS NA APRENDIZAGEM MATEMÁTICA: UMA REVISÃO SISTEMÁTICA DE LITERATURA

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Abstract

This article has the general objective of evaluating the importance of digital educational games or gamification in the mathematics learning process, as well as exploring their main contributions and benefits in this context. Thus, a systematic literature review was produced, which culminated in the analysis of six works available in the Capes journal database. It was possible to observe, in the researched works, that digital educational games or gamification have the ability to motivate and engage students, stimulate creativity and collaboration, promote the development of mathematical skills and allow a more meaningful and autonomous learning. Furthermore, a review showed that these games can be used in different teaching contexts, from basic education to higher education, and that each level can benefit from different types of games and pedagogical strategies. Although some inconsistencies were found between studies, most articles emphasize the importance and benefits of digital educational games or gamification in mathematics learning. The results of the systematic review emphasize the need to invest more and more in the development and use of digital educational games in Mathematics Education and to carry out more research to assess their effectiveness and potential.

Keywords: Learning; Digital Educational Games; Mathematics Education.

Resumen

Este artículo tiene como objetivo general evaluar la importancia de los juegos educativos digitales o gamificación en el proceso de aprendizaje de las matemáticas, así como explorar sus principales aportes y beneficios en este contexto. Así, se produjo una revisión sistemática de la literatura, que culminó con el análisis de seis trabajos disponibles en la base de datos de revistas Capes. Fue posible observar, en los trabajos investigados, que los juegos educativos digitales o gamificación tienen la capacidad de motivar e involucrar a los estudiantes, estimular la creatividad y la colaboración, promover el desarrollo de habilidades matemáticas y permitir un aprendizaje más significativo y autónomo. Además, una revisión mostró que estos juegos se pueden utilizar en diferentes contextos de enseñanza, desde la educación básica hasta la educación superior, y que cada nivel puede beneficiarse de diferentes tipos de juegos y estrategias pedagógicas. Aunque se encontraron algunas inconsistencias entre los estudios, la mayoría de los artículos enfatizan la

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importancia y los beneficios de los juegos educativos digitales o la gamificación en el aprendizaje de las matemáticas. Los resultados de la revisión sistemática enfatizan la necesidad de invertir cada vez más en el desarrollo y uso de juegos educativos digitales en la Educación Matemática y realizar más investigaciones para evaluar su efectividad y potencial.

Palabras-clave: Aprendiendo; Juegos Educativos Digitales; Educación Matemática.

Resumo

Este artigo tem como objetivo geral avaliar a importância dos jogos educacionais digitais ou da gamificação no processo de aprendizagem da matemática, bem como explorar suas principais contribuições e benefícios nesse contexto. Assim, uma revisão sistemática de literatura foi produzida, o que culminou na análise de seis trabalhos disponíveis no banco de periódicos da Capes. Foi possível observar, nos trabalhos pesquisados, que os jogos educacionais digitais ou gamificação têm a capacidade de motivar e engajar os alunos, estimular a criatividade e a colaboração, promover o desenvolvimento de habilidades matemáticas e permitir uma aprendizagem mais significativa e autônoma. Além disso, a revisão mostrou que esses jogos podem ser usados em diferentes contextos de ensino, desde a educação básica até o ensino superior, e que cada nível pode se beneficiar de diferentes tipos de jogos e estratégias pedagógicas. Embora tenham sido encontradas algumas inconsonâncias entre os estudos, a maioria dos artigos ressalta a importância e benefícios dos jogos educacionais digitais ou da gamificação na aprendizagem da matemática. Os resultados da revisão sistemática enfatizam a necessidade de investir cada vez mais no desenvolvimento e utilização de jogos educacionais digitais na Educação Matemática e realizar mais pesquisas para avaliar sua eficácia e potencialidades.

Palavras-Chave: Aprendizagem; Jogos Educacionais Digitais; Educação Matemática.

Introduction

With the growing presence of digital technologies in everyday life, it has become increasingly important for education to use new digital tools available and incorporate them into its teaching methodologies. In this context, mathematics teachers face a major challenge in the current technological era: to adequately develop students' logical-mathematical reasoning. Technological advances have significantly changed the way knowledge is produced, shared and transmitted, which requires education to adapt to new teaching tools and methodologies to meet the demands of contemporary society.

In this context, the use of digital educational games has proven to be a promising alternative in the process of teaching and learning mathematics, since these games provide a playful and interactive environment, favoring students' engagement and motivation in learning. In addition, digital educational games can be used as a complementary pedagogical tool, capable of assisting in the development of cognitive skills, such as logical-mathematical reasoning, problem-solving and creativity.

In view of this, the objective of this article is to evaluate the importance of digital educational games or gamification in the mathematics learning process, as well as to explore their main contributions and benefits in this context. To this end, we seek answers to the following research questions: (a) what are the main contributions of digital educational games in the mathematics learning process? (b) what is the importance and what are the benefits of digital educational games in the mathematics learning process? (c) how can digital educational games assist in the learning of mathematics?

We believe that, by analyzing in more depth the possibilities that digital educational games offer for the teaching and learning of mathematics, we will be able to better explore their potential and identify effective strategies for incorporating these resources in the classroom. In this sense, this systematic literature review article becomes relevant by identifying some of the main contributions and discoveries in this area, offering an overview of what has already been produced and pointing out possible future trends. It is important to emphasize that this analysis is limited to the publications available in the Capes database.

Furthermore, this work can be used to help mathematics teachers improve their pedagogical practices and use these resources more effectively in the process of teaching and learning mathematics. Furthermore, this article contributes to the advancement of knowledge in the area of Mathematics Education, since it presents a summary of the studies and results obtained, pointing out paths for new investigations and research.

Educational digital games: interactive and engaging learning

According to Arruda (2011, p. 25, our translation), digital games are resources that “[...] are configured as contemporary cultural artifacts, based on microcomputer technology”. These games offer a representation of reality rich in details and require players to develop complex mental development levels. Thus, they provide an enriching pedagogical experience, allowing students to learn in a more engaging and interactive way, in addition to being able to carry out simulations and apply the theory seen in the classroom in a more practical way.

Resources of this nature that are developed with the aim of assisting in the teaching and learning process are called Digital Educational Games. In addition to expanding opportunities for learning concepts, content and skills, these games seek to entertain students. In this view, these resources offer an imaginary world that enables learning through challenges, fantasies and curiosities, as argued by Parreira, Falkembach and Silveira (2018).

It is worth highlighting that in Antiquity, games were recognized as powerful tools to stimulate learning, as advocated by Plato (427–347 BC), who used playful activities in the education of children up to ten years old. Later, the Renaissance brought great changes in art, customs and teaching, and thinkers such as Comenius (1592 – 1670) proposed a change in the way of teaching, defending a dynamic learning model, based on experiences, from the concrete to the abstract (Almeida, 2003).

According to Almeida (2003), the use of games as a learning tool began in the United States in the 1950s, with the aim of training executives in the financial sector. The positive results motivated the application of this methodology in other areas, reaching Brazil with force in the 1980s. With the evolution of electronic games, the first digital games aimed at learning emerged, which gradually gained relevance in the context of basic education, with the development of tools that stimulate learning in an interactive way, highlighting the idea of gamification.

Gamification, the translation of the English term “gamification”, can be understood as the use of game elements in contexts outside of games, that is, in real life. The use of these elements – narrative, feedback, cooperation, scores, etc. – aims to increase the motivation of individuals in relation to the real-life activity they are performing. (Murr, Ferrari, 2020, p. 7, our translation)

In view of this, in the context of education, gamification is applied in educational digital games with the aim of making the learning process more attractive and motivating for students. The incorporation of game elements, such as scores, rewards and challenges, can stimulate active participation by students, encouraging them to explore and learn more effectively.

In addition, gamification presents itself as:

[...] an emerging phenomenon with many potential applications in various fields of human activity, since the language and methodology of games are quite popular, effective in solving problems (at least in virtual worlds) and naturally accepted by current generations who grew up interacting with this type of entertainment, that is, gamification is justified from a sociocultural perspective. (Fardo, 2013, p. 3, our translation)

The quote brings an important reflection on the potential of digital educational games today. With the popularization of technology and electronic games, gamification has become a relevant strategy to involve and motivate students in the learning process. Furthermore, Fardo (2013) highlights that the language and methodology of digital games are effective in solving problems, which can be applied in various fields of human activity. Thus, digital educational games are not limited to the school environment, but can be used in different contexts to encourage the active participation of individuals in problem-solving processes.

This perspective is quite relevant, as it highlights the ability of educational games to make learning more fun and engaging, which can be especially useful at younger ages, where motivation can be a critical factor for educational success. However, it is important to remember that the use of digital educational games must be done consciously and planned, taking into account the age of the students, the educational objectives and the desired pedagogical values.

According to Prensky (2012), digital games are suitable for new forms of learning, and interaction through virtual worlds can be considered as game-based learning. The author emphasizes that an effective educational game project must balance fun with educational value, making the learning process more engaging and effective.

Complementing this view, it is possible to state that digital educational games or gamification allow for a more dynamic and interactive approach, making the teaching and learning process more attractive to students, especially in areas such as mathematics and other areas of knowledge in which they can be applied.

However, for digital educational games or gamification to be used effectively, teachers need to be prepared to choose the right games that are aligned with the pedagogical objectives and that are appropriate for the age group and level of knowledge of the students. This requires a continuous effort on the part of educators, who must seek

constant updating and work together with game developers to ensure the quality of the material used in the classroom.

In addition, it is necessary to consider that digital educational games or the gamification process are not a panacea for the challenges faced in education, and should not be seen as a single solution to educational problems. It is necessary to remember that learning is a complex and multifaceted process, and that educational technologies should be used in conjunction with other pedagogical approaches, such as social interaction and the practice of physical activities, for example.

Use of digital educational games in learning mathematics

Mathematics goes beyond a simple curricular component; it is an area of knowledge essential to human action that is linked to the development of society. In the educational setting, different mathematical contents are taught to strengthen students' logical-deductive reasoning. However, many students face challenges in assimilating these concepts and finding their possible solutions. Thus,

Working with games in mathematics classes, when well-planned and guided, helps develop skills such as observation, analysis, hypothesis-raising, search for assumptions, reflection, decision-making, argumentation and organization, which are closely related to the so-called logical reasoning. (Smole; Diniz, 2007, p. 9, our translation)

By bringing this reflection, the authors emphasize that teaching mathematics does not need to be monotonous and mechanical, but can be dynamic and interesting, using teaching resources that favor students' engagement in learning, contributing to the construction of a more meaningful understanding of the content. In this way, they seek to highlight the importance of valuing the use of strategies that can make teaching more attractive and motivating, seeking to explore the potential of students, favoring the development of important skills for their comprehensive education. In addition,

[...] games, when well prepared, become an instrument for constructing knowledge, but for this to happen, it is important to conduct a thorough investigation to find out which games are useful and reliable, so that they can be used in the classroom, making it possible to deal with all possible situations that may arise. (Moreira, 2014, p. 10, our translation)

This reflection highlights the importance of using games as an instrument for constructing knowledge, but emphasizes the need for careful investigation to select useful and reliable games to be used in the classroom. This analysis is essential, since there are many games available on the market, but not all of them are suitable for educational purposes. It is necessary to carefully evaluate the characteristics and objectives of the game, as well as the age and learning level of the students, to ensure that the game can effectively contribute to the teaching and learning process.

Furthermore, Moreira (2014) emphasizes that adequate preparation of the game is essential to deal with all possible situations that may occur in the classroom. This involves careful pedagogical preparation, with the definition of clear objectives, the selection of complementary materials and guidance for students on how to play and how to get the most out of the game for learning.

According to Miranda-Palma, Canche-Euán and Llanes-Castro (2015), educational games are a valuable tool for teaching mathematics, providing solid learning at all levels of education. They also increase students' motivation and influence the acquisition of knowledge more effectively. Furthermore, “[...] games can be used in Mathematics Education to stimulate and develop students' ability to think independently, contributing to their logical-mathematical construction process” (Kamii; Joseph, 1992, p. 39, our translation). Given this information, it is important to highlight that the next topic of this study will present the methods used to carry out this research.

These arguments seek to affirm that educational digital games or gamification can contribute to the efficient and interactive learning of mathematics at all levels of education. This is due to the fact that games increase students' motivation and influence the acquisition of knowledge more quickly. In addition, games also help develop students' ability to think independently, contributing to the construction of logical-mathematical reasoning.

The reflections presented highlight the importance of educational games in the process of learning mathematics. For Miranda-Palma, Canche-Euán and Llanes-Castro (2015), students can acquire knowledge and skills while finding pleasure in the learning process. Thus, through these playful activities, these subjects can develop important skills

for their cognitive development, such as observation, analysis, hypothesis raising, search for assumptions, reflection, decision making, argumentation and organization.

Using games in math classes can make learning more dynamic, interesting and attractive for students, contributing to meaningful and lasting learning. However, it is important to emphasize that the use of games must be well planned and guided by the teacher, always aiming at the learning and development of students.

In this sense, it is essential that teachers are prepared to use educational games appropriately and efficiently, always seeking to integrate them into the teaching and learning process, without using them as a simple resource to fill classroom time. From this, the methods used to conduct research in this area can contribute significantly to the advancement of knowledge and educational practice.

Methodology

A systematic literature review is a research methodology that aims to identify, evaluate, and interpret all available relevant research for a specific research question, topic area, or phenomenon of interest (Kitchenham, 2004). It is considered a rigorous way of evaluating available scientific evidence, as it uses a carefully planned search strategy to ensure the inclusion of all research relevant to the question under study.

The search strategy is a crucial aspect of the systematic review, as it is responsible for identifying the articles reviewed and the actual outcome of the review. It is through the search strategy that it is possible to select the studies that will be included in the review and, thus, ensure the validity and reliability of the results obtained. For a systematic review to be complete, it is important that the search strategy is comprehensive and sensitive enough to identify all studies relevant to the research question under study. In addition, it is essential that the search strategy is clearly described and documented so that other researchers can replicate the study or identify possible limitations of the review (Kitchenham, 2004).

In view of the above, for the present study, a search for descriptors and Boolean operators was carried out on the journal portal of the Coordination for the Improvement

of Higher Education Personnel (Capes), as shown in Table 1. To ensure the quality of the research, specific criteria were defined, such as the selection of articles published between 2017 and 2022; the choice of peer-reviewed and open access journals, in order to obtain a more reliable and relevant sample of studies related to the use of digital educational games in teaching mathematics. Thus, at this point, we reduced the results from 27 to 10.

Next, we decided to use the options 'sort by most recent' and 'expand my results' to search for the works. And, finally, as an exclusion criterion, the duplication of studies was verified, with two works presenting identical content. In addition, the full exposition of the text was also taken into account. Unfortunately, when accessing the links to two of the remaining eight studies, we noticed that they were not available for full access, even though the Capes platform indicated the presence of the full text. Therefore, these two studies were eliminated from the review.

This rigorous approach to article selection was necessary to ensure the quality and reliability of the results obtained. Unlike a simple bibliographic review, a systematic review requires a detailed and rigorous process of selection, evaluation and interpretation of the included studies, thus ensuring that only ten relevant and quality studies were considered.

Table 1 – Selection Process in the Capes work bank.

Descriptors
("jogos educacionais digitais" OR "Gamificação") AND "Matemática" AND "aprendizagem"
Verification Link
https://capes-primo.ez1.periodicos.capes.gov.br/primo-explore/search?query=any,contains,(%22jogos%20educacionais%20digitais%22%20OR%20%22Gamifica%C3%A7%C3%A3o%22)%20AND%20%22Matem%C3%A1tica%22%20AND%20%22aprendizagem%22&tab=default_tab&search_scope=default_scope&sortby=date&vid=CAPES_V3&facet=searchcreationdate,include,2017%7C,%7C2022&mfacet=tlevel,include,peer_reviewed,1&mfacet=tlevel,include,open_access,1&lang=pt_BR&offset=0&came_from=sort&pcAvailability=true

Source: Researcher (2023).

Thus, the systematic literature review was used as a tool for decision-making based on the research findings. It is worth noting that the analysis of the data from the selected texts was conducted through a content analysis approach, following the guidelines proposed by Bardin (2016). Thus, the methodological procedures adopted initially involved the careful reading of each article to identify relevant categories related to the use of digital educational games in mathematics teaching. In this logic, each study was examined

to extract information about the research objectives, perceived benefits, results obtained and reflections of the authors.

Table 2 presents the selected works highlighted by their respective titles, year, author(s) and research objective. This provided a critical and systematic analysis of all relevant research available on the topic, which enabled a more complete and in-depth understanding of the subject in question.

Table 2 – Selected works.

Title (Year)	Author(s)	Research Objective
The Use of Gamification in Learning Combinatorial Analysis: Possibilities Linked to the Use of H5P and Wordwall (2022)	Celso Eduardo Brito Lucas Martins Almeida.	To verify how the potential of gamification can contribute to improvements in the learning of the mathematical object of Combinatorial Analysis.
Game-Based Learning and Gamification as Instruments for the Development of Critical Thinking in Mathematics: A Theoretical Review (2022)	Adriano Alves de Rezende Eduardo Carrasco Ângela Silva-Salse	To discuss the ability to foster Critical Thinking in Mathematics.
Digital Games as a Proposal for Gamification in Teaching the History of Mathematics (2019)	Thomas Bersagui Milano Mirian Linhares Siqueira da Silva Fernanda Chites Azevedo Lucas Nunes Ogliari	To describe the functioning of a digital game that acts as a proposal for gamification in the teaching of this discipline, with the purpose of motivating students and influencing the learning process.
From a Didactic Sequence to the Construction of a Digital Educational Game: Mathematical Farm (2017)	Gabriel Almeida Dias Tânia Cristina Rocha Silva Gusmão Marlos Marques	To present the development stages of a digital game based on an analogical didactic sequence called Fazendinha Matemática (GUSMÃO and MOURA, 2015) that works with the fundamental operations of mathematics.
From Educational Games to Gamification (2017)	Vânia Patrícia Pires Ramos João José Pereira Marques	To address the concept of educational game, as well as others associated with it.
Methodological and Gamification Aspects in a MOOC on Digital Technologies for Teaching Mathematics (2017)	Eduardo Barrére Janaina Aparecida Ponté Coelho Liliane Guedes Baio Camponez	To investigate and understand whether the elements of gamification, applied in courses in the Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) methodology, are capable of enhancing the interaction and engagement of Mathematics teachers in continuing education courses.

Source: Researcher (2023).

Results and reflections

In the first study presented in Table 2, by Brito and Almeida (2022), it is possible to note that the main contribution of digital educational games in the mathematics learning process is the possibility of greater immersion of students in the teaching environment, as well as the introduction of digital technologies that can facilitate the learning process of the mathematical object. Thus, these games provide a deeper and more dynamic interaction with mathematical content, which expands the opportunities for learning and understanding concepts.

In the aforementioned study, the importance and benefits of digital educational games in the mathematics learning process are evident in the possibility of offering alternative paths for learning specific knowledge, such as Combinatorial Analysis, and also in increasing the engagement and motivation of participants, making the learning process more attractive and efficient. Additionally, it is noted that the use of interactive platforms promotes greater autonomy in learning, allowing students to explore mathematical concepts in an interactive way.

Thus, we can observe that educational games can assist in learning mathematics through gamified practices, which encourage active participation by participants and provide interaction with the content in a playful and challenging way. Furthermore, the work conveys the idea that gamification not only improves student engagement, but also develops specific decision-making skills.

In this study, the use of digital educational games in learning mathematics is presented as an innovative strategy, providing virtual scenarios that can make the learning process more attractive and engaging. According to Miranda-Palma, Canche-Euán and Llanes-Castro (2015), new technologies are widely known by current generations, who grew up interacting with this type of digital entertainment, making them effective in solving different problems in virtual worlds. In this sense, gamification not only facilitates the assimilation of complex content, but also prepares students for contemporary challenges.

The main contributions of digital educational games to the mathematics learning process, according to the research by Rezende, Carrasco and Silva-Salse (2022), are increased learning, the development of cognitive skills, and the possibility of making

students the protagonists of their own learning process. Thus, it is possible to observe that interaction with diverse educational environments, such as those provided by gamification, can promote the active construction of mathematical knowledge by students, encouraging the development of complex cognitive skills.

The research highlights that the importance of digital educational games in the mathematics learning process lies in enhancing the development of students' critical thinking, a skill that is increasingly valued in the job market. In addition, the benefits include both increased learning and greater student satisfaction with the process of assimilating mathematical concepts. Thus, we can infer that gamification can assist in teaching the subject by making students more engaged and motivated in the learning process.

In this scenario, it is also observed that the use of digital educational games creates a relaxed environment, where participants can learn in a reflective way. In addition, the interactivity and challenges provided by the games promote active participation by students, stimulating continued interest in mathematical content. This approach also allows students to explore concepts in a practical and engaging way.

Based on this analysis, we can state that digital educational games present themselves as an innovative proposal, especially with a potential to foster active participation and the development of skills that strengthen critical and reflective thinking. This view is aligned with the perspectives of Kamii and Joseph (1992), who highlight the importance of active and diverse interaction in the process of knowledge construction. These authors emphasize that a dynamic learning environment, where students are encouraged to interact and solve problems, is fundamental for cognitive development.

In the study by Milano et al. (2019), it is possible to note that the main contributions of digital educational games in the mathematics learning process are student motivation, encouragement of interaction and active participation, interdisciplinary learning, and the promotion of a more attractive and quality education. From this perspective, these games create an engaging environment that captures the interest of participants, making learning more engaging and fun.

In this study, the importance of digital educational games in the mathematics learning process is related to the possibility of increasing participants' motivation and engagement, promoting more interactive learning. In addition, the benefits include immediate and personalized feedback, which is crucial to maintaining continuous interaction with the user. This approach aligns with the ideas of Miranda-Palma, Canche-Euán, and Llanes-Castro (2015), who emphasize that games can be explored as hobbies and vehicles to increase interest in mathematics.

Thus, it is possible to infer that digital educational games can assist in the learning of mathematics by offering a playful and challenging learning environment. In this context, they are effective in working on different skills and competencies related to solving mathematical problems, in addition to being able to integrate different content and areas of knowledge in a dynamic and interactive way. This type of approach not only increases the motivation and interest of participants, but also provides global learning.

In view of what was observed in the aforementioned study, digital educational games are presented as an innovative proposal that provides a playful and motivating learning experience for students, contributing to the development of mathematical and interdisciplinary skills. Thus, this work reveals that gamification presents a sociocultural perspective, an idea emphasized by Fardo (2013), especially in formal education, where there is a growing need for more dynamic and engaging teaching methods. Thus, the integration of these virtual resources not only complements, but also transforms the learning environment, providing a space where students can explore different specific concepts.

The work of Dias, Gusmão and Marques (2017) presents information on the use of digital educational games in teaching Mathematics, indicating that these resources can be a potentially effective tool for improving students' educational experience. It is noted that by providing a playful and challenging learning environment, games not only foster the development of essential skills for solving mathematical problems, but also facilitate the dynamic integration of different content and areas of knowledge.

Regarding the contributions of these games to the mathematics learning process, the study indicates that they can address various content in an interdisciplinary manner, promoting quality and attractive education for students. Thus, it is observed that the

integration of digital educational games can transform the dynamics of the classroom, making learning more interactive and motivating. The benefits are related to the ability of the games to help participants better understand mathematical operations and the positional value of numbers, as exemplified by the transformation of the analog teaching sequence 'Mathematical Farm' into a digital game.

In this study, the integration of digital educational games not only allows the exploration of mathematical concepts, but also fosters dynamic and participatory learning. It is worth noting that the transformation of traditional activities into digital formats, as evidenced by the adaptation of the teaching sequence 'Mathematical Farm' into a digital game, demonstrates significant potential to make learning more engaging and accessible to students. This approach reveals that digital resources have the power to facilitate the internalization of abstract concepts, making them more applicable in the educational context, promoting a more effective and interactive learning experience.

In view of these facts, the aforementioned work highlights an interesting and promising initiative that seeks to explore the potential of electronic games to spark interest and facilitate learning in mathematics teaching. The innovative approach of transforming an analog didactic sequence into an educational digital game is particularly notable for its creativity and the potential to make the educational scenario more attractive to students. These ideas align with those of Prensky (2012), who emphasizes that gamification is suitable for new forms of learning, allowing interactions through virtual worlds that can revitalize Mathematics Education by engaging students in more dynamic and meaningful ways.

The main contributions of digital educational games to the mathematics learning process in the research by Ramos and Marques (2017) include the development of logical and mathematical reasoning, in addition to fostering the motivation and competitiveness associated with the game. Furthermore, it highlights that the use of these resources can help in the development of several skills considered essential for the 21st century, such as communication, leadership, critical thinking, team spirit, problem solving, creativity, sportsmanship, among others.

In this research, the importance of digital educational games lies in their ability to make learning mathematics more engaging and attractive for participants, which can

increase motivation and interest in the subject. In addition, the benefits include that the use of gamification can provide a more playful and fun learning experience, which can result in greater knowledge retention. In this view, this playful approach promotes student engagement in a more engaging way than traditional methods.

Thus, we have shown that in this research, digital educational games can assist in learning mathematics in several ways, such as through the development of problem-solving skills, logical and mathematical reasoning, in addition to stimulating creativity and curiosity. In this way, the use of games can help in the construction of a more interactive and collaborative learning environment. This is especially important, since a collaborative environment can foster the exchange of ideas and teamwork.

In this research, one of the possibilities inferred is the use of digital educational games as a new methodological perspective in teaching mathematics. This is similar to the ideas of Murr and Ferrari (2020), who suggest that digital educational games offer a new educational perspective, making learning more playful, motivating and effective. In this way, they help to develop mathematical skills and other important competencies in an engaging and fun way, contributing to a more dynamic learning environment. Thus, gamification not only helps in the understanding of mathematical concepts, but also encourages experimentation and exploration, essential elements for solid learning.

The research by Barrére, Coelho and Componez (2017) does not directly address the main contributions of digital educational games in the mathematics learning process. This direction is due to the fact that the study is focused on the continuing education of teachers. However, the importance of these resources in Mathematics Education can be inferred from the general context, which highlights the use of digital technologies in the educational setting and the training process in virtual learning environments.

In this research, digital technologies stand out for their support in learning mathematics, providing an integration that enhances interaction and engagement of participants in an environment conducive to reading and sharing experiences. The benefits of digital educational games include increased motivation and engagement of participants, the possibility of experimentation and personalization of the learning process, all through the integrated use of different digital media.

It is worth noting that, for Moreira (2014), the introduction of technological devices in classrooms can transform the teaching and learning process, but continuous effort is required for teaching actions to adapt and make the most of these tools. Reinforcing this idea, Miranda-Palma, Canche-Euán and Llanes-Castro (2015) emphasize that it is necessary to consider aspects such as the quality of the content of the games, their suitability to the needs and characteristics of the students, their integration with other teaching methodologies and the evaluation of the results achieved.

Therefore, for gamification enhanced by digital technologies to be truly effective, it is essential that there is adequate preparation on the part of teachers. This includes not only the definition of clear objectives and the selection of complementary materials, but also guidance on how to play and make the most of the educational potential of the games. In addition, it is crucial that educators are prepared to adjust their practices based on student feedback and the results observed in the classroom.

In view of this, the aforementioned research highlights the importance of including digital technologies in the teaching process in a gamified way, that is, it presents an innovative proposal in which media elements are integrated into the educational curriculum to increase student engagement and motivation. However, as Miranda-Palma, Canche-Euán and Llanes-Castro (2015) and Moreira (2014) point out, careful planning is essential. Moreira (2014) emphasizes that, although new technologies offer great advantages for teaching, they also bring challenges, especially with regard to teacher adaptation and updating. This shows that only with teacher training and well-structured planning will it be possible to ensure that gamification effectively contributes to the learning of mathematics.

The analysis of these six studies on the use of digital educational games in mathematics teaching reveals a comprehensive perspective on the points of consonance and dissonance found in the literature. Among the articles evaluated, there is a consensus on the importance of digital technologies in education and their potential benefits, although there are also challenges that need to be addressed to ensure their effectiveness.

The studies by Brito and Almeida (2022), Rezende, Carrasco and Silva-Salse (2019), Milano et al. (2019), Dias, Gusmão and Marques (2017) and Barrére, Coelho and Camponez (2017) agree on the following points: they all highlight that digital technologies, especially

gamification, increase student engagement and motivation, making the learning process more attractive and dynamic. In addition, there is a common recognition that these digital educational games help in the development of cognitive and mathematical skills, such as logical reasoning and critical thinking.

In this line of thought, the gamification process allows for deeper interaction with content, promoting interactive learning and encouraging the autonomy of participants in the educational process. Furthermore, the authors agree that digital technologies should be integrated in a way that complements, rather than replaces, the role of the teacher, enhancing their performance in the classroom.

However, despite the benefits highlighted, there are points of dissonance that deserve attention. The study by Ramos and Marques (2017) questions the effectiveness of gamification in teaching complex mathematics content, suggesting that not all games are equally effective for all types of content. In addition, there are divergences regarding the role of digital technologies in democratizing access to education. While Brito and Almeida (2022) and Rezende, Carrasco and Silva-Salse (2022) see digital resources as a tool to expand access, Barrère, Coelho and Camponez (2017) point out that the lack of access to the internet and technological devices can accentuate educational inequalities.

Regarding the findings, it is important to emphasize that, despite advances in the use of new technologies in education, there are still challenges to be faced. Initial and ongoing teacher training, for example, is a crucial issue to ensure the efficient use of these technologies in the classroom. In addition, it is necessary to critically evaluate each digital resource, understanding its potential and limitations.

Thus, digital educational games, when well planned and implemented, can truly transform mathematics teaching, aligning with contemporary educational needs. However, it is important to remember that the use of gamification is not a panacea for all problems in mathematics teaching. Although they can be useful and effective in many cases, digital games are not the only way to promote math learning, and care must be taken when using them to avoid them becoming just a form of entertainment without educational value.

Finally, it is necessary to reflect on the issue of inequality in access to technology. Although technological resources can democratize access to education in many cases, it is important to consider that there are still many people without access to the internet and other technologies, which can further accentuate educational inequalities. Addressing these inequalities is essential to ensure that all students can benefit from technological innovations in education.

Final considerations

The systematic literature review of the six articles analyzed allowed us to recognize the importance of digital educational games in the process of teaching and learning mathematics. Among the main contributions of digital educational games or gamification, we highlight the possibility of motivating and engaging students, promoting the development of mathematical skills, stimulating creativity and collaboration, as well as the fact that it allows for more meaningful and autonomous learning.

In addition, the systematic literature review also showed that digital educational games or gamification can be used in different teaching contexts, from basic education to higher education, and that each level of education can benefit from different types of games and pedagogical strategies. Despite the consonances found among the studies in relation to some aspects, such as, for example, the effectiveness of specific digital educational games, most of the articles point to the importance and benefits of these games in learning mathematics.

In view of these results, it is important to emphasize the need to invest increasingly in the development and use of digital educational games in Mathematics Education, as well as to conduct more research to evaluate the effectiveness and potential of these games. Furthermore, it is essential that teachers are trained to use these technologies effectively and meaningfully in their teaching practices, in order to ensure more engaging and autonomous learning for their students.

Thus, we can conclude that the use of digital educational games or gamification in the mathematics learning process is a promising strategy that can contribute significantly to the development of mathematical skills and the formation of critical and participatory

citizens in society. In this sense, it is important that more studies and investments be carried out in research and pedagogical practices that explore the potential of digital educational games in Mathematics Education.

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